

COLD DESERTS

MARINE WEST COAST FOREST

MEDITERRANEAN CALIFORNIA

SOUTH CENTRAL SEMIARID PRAIRIES

UPPER GILA MOUNTAINS

WARM DESERTS

WEST-CENTRAL SEMIARID PRAIRIES

WESTERN CORDILLERA

WESTERN SIERRA MADRE PIEDMONT

COLD DESERTS

Fire size

Vegetation type burned

Fire seasonality

Structure loss

Structure loss rate

Structure loss seasonality

MARINE WEST COAST FOREST

Fire size

Vegetation type burned

Fire seasonality

Structure loss

Structure loss rate

Structure loss seasonality

MEDITERRANEAN CALIFORNIA

Fire size

Vegetation type burned

Fire seasonality

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Structure loss rate

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SOUTH CENTRAL SEMIARID PRAIRIES

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UPPER GILA MOUNTAINS

Fire size

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Fire seasonality

Structure loss

Structure loss rate

Structure loss seasonality

WARM DESERTS

Fire size

Vegetation type burned

Fire seasonality

Structure loss

Structure loss rate

Structure loss seasonality

WEST-CENTRAL SEMIARID PRAIRIES

Fire size

Vegetation type burned

Fire seasonality

Structure loss

Structure loss rate

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WESTERN CORDILLERA

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WESTERN SIERRA MADRE PIEDMONT

Fire size

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Structure loss seasonality

Proportion of total

Proportion of total